

Research Article

Life form and leaf size spectra of vegetation in Kotli Hills, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (Pakistan)

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ABSTRACT

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The flora of District Kotli consists of 97 plant species belonging to 47 families. The biological spectrum showed that therophytes (27.83 %), was the dominant life form of the area. It was followed by hemicryptophytes (20.61 %), nanophanerophytes (18.55 %), Geophytes (12.64%) and megaphanerophytes (12.37%). Chamaephytes (2.06%) and lianas (3.09%) were low in number. The leaf size spectra of plant communities consisted of microphylls (25.77 %), mesophylls (8.24 %), leptophylls (35.05 %), nanophylls (28.86 %) and megaphylls (3.60 %). The dominance of Therophytes and Leptophylls indicate that the area was a subtropical type.

Keywords:

Flora, Leaf size, life form, Kotli,

Therophytes, Leptophylls,

Microphylls

1. INTRODUCTION

A life form is characterized by plant adaptation to certain ecological conditions (Mera *et al.* 1999). This study is an important part of vegetation description, ranking next to floristic composition (Cain, 1950). Life form of vegetation is to a certain extent, an indicator of the climate and is also useful in comparing geographically, widely distributed plant communities. Furthermore, it is traditionally being used to describe world vegetation type at community level (Raunkiaer, 1934). The life form and leaf size spectra are useful attributes which have been widely used in vegetation description. The life form spectra are indicators of micro and macroclimate (Shimwell, 1971). Similarly leaf size classes have been found to be very useful for plant associations. The leaf size knowledge may help in the understanding of physiological processes of plants and plant communities (Oosting, 1956). Little work has been done on the life form and leaf size spectra. The only references for Azad Jammu and Kashmir are Malik (1986), Malik and Malik (2004) and Malik *et al.*, (2007) who gave spectra for Kotli, Ganga Chotti and Bedorri Hills (District Bagh) Azad Jammu and Kashmir.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

The investigated area was divided into thirteen plant communities on the basis of altitude and physiognomic difference. Life form tells us about the climate of area. The plants were classified after Raunkiaer (1934) and Muller and Ellenberg (1974). The leaf size knowledge, help us in understanding the physiological process of plants and plant communities and is useful in classifying the associations of plants. Plants were divided in to (A) microphyll, (B) mesophyll, (C) leptophyll, (D) nanophyll and (E) megaphyll. For this estimation in the area, the Raunkiaer (1934) diagram was used. The survey was done during monsoon, 2009. The area ranges in between 590 m and 1860 m from the mean sea level.

3. RESULTS

1 - *Olea-Malvastrum-Adhatoda* community : The community harboured at an elevation of 590m, had a share of 18.18% Megaphanerophytes, 9.09% nanophanerophytes, 36.36% therophytes, 27.27% hemicryptophytes, 4.54% geophytes and lianas each. The Therophytes were dominant.

2 – *Acacia- Lespedeza* community: At 620m, the *Acacia- Lespedeza* community comprised of 18 species. Out of which 22.22% were megaphanerophytes, 16.67% were nanophanerophytes, 38.89% were therophytes, 11.11% were hemicryptophytes, geophytes and lianas were 5.55% each. The Therophytes were significant.

3 - *Brachiaria-Themeda* community: This community was reported from Badana hills at an elevation of 650m. In this community there were 20.83%

megaphanerophytes, 12.50% nanophanerophytes, 29.17% therophytes, 20.83% hemicryptophytes, 12.50% geophytes and 4.17% lianas.

4 - *Themeda-Pinus- Dodonaea* community: At an elevation of 850m, 30 species were recognized. Out of which 16.66% were megaphanerophytes, 10% were nanophanerophytes, 20% therophytes, 26.67% hemicryptophytes, 16.67% geophytes, 3.33% chameophytes and 6.67% lianas. The Hemicryptophytes was recorded as the dominant life form.

5 - *Themeda-Pinus-Olea* community: This community comprised of 32 species at an elevation of 970m. 15.62% were megaphanerophytes, nanophanerophytes, therophytes and geophytes each, 28.12% hemicryptophytes, 3.12% chameophytes and 6.25% lianas. Hemicryptophytes were significant.

6 - *Pinus* community: This community was recorded at an elevation of 1090 from Panagh-Galli. Totally there were 34 species. Out of which 15.62% were megaphanerophytes, 20.59% nanophanerophytes, 32.35% therophytes, 26.47% hemicryptophytes, 8.82% geophytes and 2.94% lianas. The dominant life form was the hemicryptophytes.

7 - *Pinus* community: *Pinus* community was reported at an elevation of 1200m from Pagwar- Mohra. In this community there were 5% megaphanerophytes and chameophytes each, 10% nanophanerophytes, geophytes and lianas each, 25% therophytes and 35% hemicryptophytes. The significant life form was the hemicryptophytes.

8 - *Pinus* community: 30 species were present in this community at an elevation of 1300m. Out of which megaphanerophytes, nanophanerophytes and geophytes have equal distribution with 13.33%. Therophytes were 26.67%, hemicryptophytes were 30%, and lianas were 3.33%. The Hemicryptophytes were significant.

9 - *Pinus* community: This community comprised of 28 species at an elevation of 1400m. Out of which 14.28% were megaphanerophytes, 21.42% nanophanerophytes, 32.14% therophytes, 25% hemicryptophytes and 7.14% geophytes. The Therophytes were dominant.

10 - *Dicliptera* community: At an elevation of 1500m 27 species were recognized. In this community there were 7.41% megaphanerophytes, 18.52% nanophanerophytes, 33.33% therophytes, 25.92% hemicryptophytes, 11.11% geophytes and 3.70% chameophytes. The Therophytes were recorded as the dominant life form.

11 - *Pinus* community: *Pinus* community was reported from Pir- Klinjer at an elevation of 1620m. Totally there were 25 species. Out of which 8% were megaphanerophytes, 20% nanophanerophytes, 24% therophytes, 32% hemicryptophytes and 8% geophytes.

Chameophytes and lianas have equal share of 4%. Hemicryptophytes were significant.

12 - Pinus community: This community was recorded at an elevation of 1735m from Pir- Lasoora. Megaphanerophytes, nanophanerophytes and therophytes have equal distribution (13.79%), hemicryptophytes were 34.48%, chameophytes and lianas were 3.44% each. The dominant life form was the hemicryptophytes.

13 - Rubus-Quercus-Pinus community: At an elevation of 1860m, 35 species were recognized. Out of which 8.57% were megaphanerophytes, 17.14% nanophanerophytes, 25.71% hemicryptophytes 22.86 geophytes and 2.86% lianas.

Total number of species in the investigated area was 97. Out of which 12.37% were Megaphanerophytes, 18.55% nanophanerophytes, 27.83% therophytes, 20.61% hemicryptophytes, 12.64% geophytes and 2.06% chameophytes. Only 3.0.9% was Lianas. Therophyte was the dominant life form in the area followed by hemicryptophyte.(Fig: 1)

Table: 1 Percentage of life form of different plant communities recorded from Kotli Hills during Monsoon 2010

S.No	Community	Height	Total sp	Mp		Np		Th		H		G		Ch		L	
				No	%	No	%	No	%								
1	O-M-A	590	22	4	18.18	2	9.09	8	36.36	6	27.27	1	4.54	-	-	1	4.54
2	A-L	620	18	4	22.22	3	16.67	7	38.89	2	11.11	1	5.55	-	-	1	5.55
3	B-T	650	24	5	20.83	3	12.50	7	29.17	5	20.83	3	12.50	-	-	1	4.17
4	T-P-D	850	30	5	16.66	3	10	6	20	8	26.67	5	16.67	1	3.33	2	6.67
5	T-P-O	970	32	5	15.62	5	15.62	5	15.62	9	28.12	5	15.62	1	3.12	2	6.25
6	P	1090	34	3	8.82	7	20.59	1	3.23	9	26.47	3	8.82	-	-	1	2.94
7	P	1200	20	1	5	2	10	5	25	7	35	2	10	1	5	2	10
8	P	1300	30	4	13.33	4	13.33	8	26.67	9	30	4	13.33	-	-	1	3.33
9	P	1400	28	4	14.28	6	21.42	9	32.14	7	25	2	7.14	-	-	-	-
10	D	1500	27	2	7.41	5	18.52	9	33.33	7	25.92	3	11.11	1	3.70	-	-
11	P	1620	25	2	8	5	20	6	24	8	32	2	8	1	4	1	4
12	P	1735	29	4	13.79	4	13.79	4	13.79	1	3.44	5	17.24	1	3.44	1	3.44
13	R-Q-P	1860	35	3	8.57	6	17.14	8	22.86	9	25.71	8	22.86	1	2.86	-	-

Fig. 1. Life form of Kotli Hills

Communities on the Basis of Leaf spectra

1 - *Olea-Malvastrum-Adhatoda* community: This community reported at an elevation of 590m, 31.82% were leptophylls, 27.27% were nanophylls, 22.73% were microphylls, and 18.18% were mesophyll. Leptophylls were recorded dominant in this community.

2 – *Acacia- Lespedeza* community: At an elevation of 620m, leptophylls and microphylls were recorded as dominant in this community with an equal share of 33.33%. 22.22% were nanophylls, 9.09% were mesophylls.

3 - *Brachiaria-Themeda* community: There were 24 species in this community. Out of which 25% were leptophylls, 37.5% were nanophylls, 33.33% microphylls, and 4.16% were mesophyll. Nanophylls were significant.

4 - *Themeda-Pinus- Dodonaea* community: This community consists of 30 species at an elevation of . In this community leptophylls were 30%, nanophylls were 36.67%, microphylls were 26.67%, and 6.66% were mesophyll. Microphylls was dominant.

5 - *Themeda-Pinus-Olea* community: In this community, the total species were 32. Dominant species were microphyll (34.37%) followed by leptophylls (31.25%), nanophylls (25%), mesophyll (9.37%).

6 - *Pinus* community: This community was recorded at an elevation of 1090 from Panagh-Galli. In total there were 34 species. Out of which 29.41% were leptophylls, 35.29% were nanophylls, 32.35% were microphylls and

2.94% were mesophyll. The Nanophylls were dominant in this community.

7 - *Pinus* community: *Pinus* community was reported at an elevation of 1200m from Pagwar- Mohra. In this community there were 50% leptophylls, 25% nanophylls and 25% microphylls. Leptophylls was significant.

8 - *Pinus* community: 30 species were found present in this community at an elevation of 1300m. Out of which leptophylls were 30%, nanophylls and microphylls have equal share of 33.33% and mesophyll were 3.33%. The nanophylls and microphylls were dominant in this community.

9 - *Pinus* community: This community comprised of 28 species at an elevation of 1400m. Out of which 32.14% were leptophylls, 46.42% nanophylls, and 21.42% microphylls. Mesophylls were absent in this community.

10 - *Dicliptera* community: At an elevation of 1500m, 27 species were recognized. In this community 37.04% were leptophylls, 33.33% were nanophylls, 25.92% were microphyll and 3.70% were mesophylls. Leptophylls was dominant in this community.

11 - *Pinus* community: *Pinus* community was reported from Pir- Klinjer at an elevation of 1620m. In total, there were 25 species. Out of which leptophylls were 40%, nanophylls were 36% and microphylls were 24%. Leptophylls were significant.

12 - *Pinus* community: This community was recorded at an elevation of 1735m from Pir- Lasoora. Leptophylls and microphylls (26.67%) were equally distributed.

Nanophylls were dominant in this community with a share of 46.67%.

13 - *Rubus-Quercus-Pinus* community; At an elevation of 1860m, 35 species were recognized. Out of which 40% were leptophylls, 34.28% were nanophylls,

20% were microphylls and 5.71% were mesophyll. Leptophylls were significant in the community. As a whole the investigated area compared of 97 plant species. Leptophylls (35.05%) were dominant followed by Nanophylls(28.86%) and Microphylls (25.77%),. Only 8.24% were Mesophylls. (Fig: 2.)

Table: 2 Percentage of leaf spectra recorded from Kotli Hills during Monsoon 2010

S.No	Community	Height (m)	Total sp	L		N		Mi		Me	
				No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%
1	O-M-A	590	22	7	31.82	6	27.27	5	22.73	4	18.18
2	A-L	620	18	6	33.33	4	22.22	6	33.33	2	9.09
3	B- T	650	24	6	25	9	37.5	8	33.33	1	4.16
4	T-P-D	850	30	9	30	11	36.67	8	26.67	2	6.66
5	T-P-O	970	32	10	31.25	8	25	11	34.37	3	9.37
6	P	1090	34	10	29.41	12	35.29	11	32.35	1	2.94
7	P	1200	20	10	50	5	25	5	25	-	-
8	P	1300	30	9	30	10	33.33	10	33.33	1	3.33
9	P	1400	28	9	32.14	13	46.42	6	21.42	-	-
10	D	1500	27	10	37.04	9	33.33	7	25.92	1	3.70
11	P	1620	25	10	40	9	36	6	24	-	-
12	P	1735	29	8	27.59	14	48.27	7	24.13	-	-
13	R-Q-P	1860	35	14	40	12	34.28	7	20	2	5.71

Fig: 2. Leaf spectra of Kotli Hills

4. DISCUSSION.

A life form is characterized by plants adaptation to certain ecological conditions (Mera *et al*, 1999). This study is an important part of vegetation description ranking next to floristic composition (Cain, 1950). Life forms of the vegetation to a certain extent, is an indicator of the climate and is also helpful in comparing geographically, widely distributed plant communities. It has traditionally been used to describe world vegetation formation type at community level (Raunkiaer, 1934). Climate of a region is characterized by life form while the biological spectrum of the region exceeds the percentage of the same life form in the normal biological spectrum. However biotic agencies are the chief causes for changing the biological spectrum in a given floristic zone i.e. Agricultural Practices, grazing and deforestation. In the investigated area, the life form

spectra of the different plant communities indicated that hemicryptophytic and therophytic species were dominant during the spring and monsoon seasons.

Cain and Castro, (1959) and Shimwell (1971) reported that hemicryptophytes indicates temperate zones whereas therophytes are indicators of desert climate and geophytes are indicators of the Mediterranean climate. The climate of study area differs from subtropical to humid type vegetation at different altitudes. In the investigated area Therophyte species were dominant followed by Hemicryptophytes. These results are in agreement with Malik 1986, Malik and Malik 2004 Ajaib *et al*. 2008 Therophytes are indicators of subtropical and disturbed vegetation. While Hemicryptophytes are indicators of humid condition.

The area of Kotli lies in subtropical dry type condition. The dominance of therophytes reflects that

environmental conditions or human influences are not well suited to the Phanerophytes. Severe deforestation, overgrazing, soil erosion and human influence in the area reduces the macrophylls and so therophytes appear to occupy the vacant niches (Ajaib *et al.* 2008). The investigated area has heavy biotic pressure due to wood extraction which can be seen from the age class at the time of sampling. Moreover, at the time of sampling the season suited to annual. Monsoon generally favors for rapid explosion of annual plants. Hemicyptophytes which are present in high numbers is due to the moist nature of the habitat.

Malik *et al.*, 1996 recorded that in the moist parts of Dirkot, hemicyptes are the dominant life form. From the analysis, it can be seen that phanerophytes might have been the dominant life form before degradation. The degraded vegetation generally supports the therophytic and hemicyptophytic types of vegetation (Malik 1986.; Ram and Arya, 1991). Factors like deforestation, overgrazing and urbanization remain contributing factors in the loss of vegetation in the area but over the years, many other factors of vegetation depletion emerged as the natural and artificial factors of vegetation depletion. (Malik and Malik 2004 and Ajaib *et al.* 2008)

The leaf size spectrum of these communities showed that the overall vegetation of Kotli is dominated by leptophylls and nanophylls. The results are in agreement with Malik *et al.*, 1986. The decrease in leaf size indicates dry and xeric conditions. Microphyll is also reported as a dominant life form in higher altitudes due to low temperature, high rainfall and moist condition. Generally, lower altitudes support small leaves in lower belt and large leaves in upper niches. Leptophylls and nanophylls are the characteristics of hot deserts while microphylls are the characteristics of steppes (Cain & Castro, 1959; Tareen & Qadir, 1993). The present study shows that leptophylls were high at the foothills while nanophylls and microphylls were present in high altitudes.

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